

MICROSTRUCTURAL INFLUENCE ON THE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS IN TRANSVERSELY LOADED UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The transverse mechanical properties of unidirectional composites are estimated taken into account the geometrical arrangement of inhomogeneities. The stress field in a material with randomly dispersed fibers is solved by applying an iterative procedure, which can include the varying interaction between fibers. Using a superposition technique, the stress intensity factors are determined for a crack situated among the fibers. The limit for short-range interaction is estimated by calculating the stress intensity factors for a crack located in the vicinity of fiber distributions. Finally, a quantifier which correlate the dispersion of fibers with the stress intensity factor of a crack is presented.

INTRODUCTION

In unidirectional composites, the geometrical arrangement of inhomogeneities is decisive for the mechanical properties in the transverse direction. Normally the problem is reduced by assuming that the arrangement of inhomogeneities has some form of regularity or assumed to be sparsely distributed. Here, each inhomogeneity is exposed to either the same amount of interaction in regular distributions or it is exposed to no interaction in the dilute distributions. Consequently, it is possible to establish a repetitious unit cell containing only a few inhomogeneities and it may be analysed thoroughly within reasonable limits. In real materials though, the dispersion of inhomogeneities is usually non-regular and in order to investigate the mechanical properties of such materials, the analysis method must take into account the exact dispersion of inhomogeneities. Due to the non-regularity the inhomogeneities are exposed to various amounts of interaction and the local stress field varies throughout the microstructure. Therefore, the present unit cell concept needs to be re-defined so that it contains enough inhomogeneities to be representative for the non-regular microstructure.

The inhomogeneities are in the present work assumed to be fibers and cracks and a method for calculating the stress field in a material with randomly dispersed fibers as well as determining the stress intensity factors for a crack, situated among the fibers, must be established. With such a method it is possible to analyse if there is any correlation between various mechanical parameters and the arrangements of fibers and cracks. A configuration, which is of interest, is the macrocrack situated in the vicinity of a fiber distribution. It is analysed how the fracture toughness of the macrocrack is affected by the dispersion of fibers. An

estimate of the short-range interaction is given by considering when the exact positions of fibers become non-influential. By applying functions of spatial statistics, which are able to distinguish between various fiber distributions a correlation function is established. The function is called the *Direct Correlation Function* and it relates the stress intensity factors of a macrocrack with the exact dispersion of fibers. Due to the localization of the phenomena the fibers, which are closest to the crack, have the largest effect and must therefore also be accounted for.

STRESS AND FRACTURE ANALYSIS

In order to determine how the non-regularity affects the transverse mechanical properties, the stress analysis method must include the interaction effects between randomly dispersed fibers. The fibers are contained within an infinite solid, which is exposed to uniform tractions at the remote boundaries. Also, a method for determining the stress intensity factors for a crack, located in the matrix material, needs to be established. Pijaudier-Cabot and Bazant[4] presented such a method and it is in the following presented briefly. The method is based upon a superposition of subproblems and take into account the varying interaction between fibers and cracks.

STRESS ANALYSIS METHOD

The stress field solution for the single fiber configuration, Fig. 1a, may be obtained analytically from the complex potential theory or the Eshelby solution, see e.g. Muskhelishvili[3], Mura[2]. Since the method must be extended to include multiple fibers an iterative procedure is applied.

Figure 1: (a) Single fiber configuration, (b) multiple fiber configuration.

A heterogeneous solid is replaced by an equivalent homogeneous solid where tractions are applied on the imaginary contour of the circular fiber and an unbalanced stress field inside this contour is added. Then the iterative procedure is applied and as a starting point the stress field in the whole solid is $\sigma = \sigma_\infty$. Using the theory of eigenstresses, Mura[2], the unbalanced stress field becomes

$$\Delta\sigma = (\mathbf{D}_m - \mathbf{D}_a)\mathbf{D}_a^{-1} \sigma \tag{1}$$

where \mathbf{D}_a and \mathbf{D}_m are the stiffness matrix for the fiber and matrix material, respectively. Tractions are applied at the imaginary contour of the fiber in order to account for the unbalanced stresses inside the fiber

$$\mathbf{p}_a = -\Delta\sigma \mathbf{n}_a \tag{2}$$

where \mathbf{n}_a is a unit outward normal to the circular contour Γ_a . The tractions are substituted by concentrated forces for which the stress field can be obtained from the complex potential theory. The forces are integrated along the circular contour and then the stress field is calculated at an arbitrary point within the contour

$$\sigma_a = \oint_{\Gamma_a} \sigma(\mathbf{p}_a) ds \quad (3)$$

The new stress field inside the fiber is obtained by

$$\sigma = \sigma_\infty + \sigma_a - \Delta\sigma \quad (4)$$

From this expression the unbalanced stress is re-calculated according to Eqn (1) and the iterations are repeated until \mathbf{p}_a does not change significantly. The method converges quite rapidly to the analytical solution and the stress field outside the fiber may be determined as follows

$$\sigma = \sigma_\infty + \sigma_a \quad (5)$$

For the multiple fibers, Fig. 1b, it is necessary to account for the interaction between fibers and a similar iterative procedure is applied. In this case the stress field in each fiber is determined as it was alone in the matrix except that the interaction from the remaining fibers is added in the calculation. Thus the stress field is based upon a superposition scheme and Eqn (4) yields

$$\sigma = \sigma_\infty + \sigma_a + \sigma_i - \Delta\sigma \quad (6)$$

where σ_i is the interacting stress field from the remaining fibers. When the stress field inside the fibers is determined, the stress field in the matrix material is calculated similarly to the single fiber solution.

DETERMINATION OF STRESS INTENSITY FACTORS

The determination of the stress intensity factors is based on a superposition scheme in which the interaction between fibers and the crack is taken into account. First the original problem is decomposed into an initial and subsidiary problem, Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Superposition scheme for the multiple fiber - single crack problem.

The initial problem consists of calculating the stress field at the imaginary contour of the crack by applying the aforementioned stress analysis method. The stress field is added in the subsidiary problem so that the configuration is in equilibrium. The subsidiary problem consists of one crack with applied tractions and the surrounding fibers. The tractions may be written as

$$\mathbf{p}_c = \tilde{\mathbf{p}}_c + \mathbf{p}_{int} \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{p}_c is the applied traction, $\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_c$ is the real yet unknown traction including the interaction from the fibers and \mathbf{p}_{int} is the interacting stress. The interacting stress arises because the real tractions interact with fibers and they are subsequently reflected back. In order to determine the real tractions Eqn (7) is averaged and the interacting stress is written as a function of real stress

$$\langle \mathbf{p}_c \rangle = (\mathbf{I} + \langle \mathbf{A} \rangle) \langle \tilde{\mathbf{p}}_c \rangle \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{A} is a transmission factor, which takes into account the whole interaction between fibers and the crack. The averaged real tractions are found by rearranging Eqn (8)

$$\langle \tilde{\mathbf{p}}_c \rangle = (\mathbf{I} + \langle \mathbf{A} \rangle)^{-1} \langle \mathbf{p}_c \rangle \quad (9)$$

Having calculated these uniform tractions for all cracks the non-uniform tractions may now be determined as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_c = \mathbf{p}_c - \mathbf{A} \langle \tilde{\mathbf{p}}_c \rangle \quad (10)$$

These tractions may now be calculated at any point of the crack line and by numerical integration the stress intensity factors are determined as

$$K_I(\pm c) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi c}} \int_{-c}^c \sqrt{\frac{c \pm x}{c \mp x}} \tilde{\mathbf{p}}_c \cdot \mathbf{n}_c dx \quad (11)$$

$$K_{II}(\pm c) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi c}} \int_{-c}^c \sqrt{\frac{c \pm x}{c \mp x}} \tilde{\mathbf{p}}_c \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_c dx \quad (12)$$

where c is the half crack length. The method is more thoroughly described in Axelsen[1].

AN ESTIMATE OF SHORT-RANGE INTERACTION

The limit for short-range interaction is in the following estimated by setting up two simple configurations with a crack located in the neighbourhood of a fiber distribution. The first configuration consists of a crack located in front of a cluster containing 26 fibers, Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Stress intensity factors for the configuration where a cluster is located in front of a crack.

The ratio between the length of the crack and the radius of fibers $c/R = 2$ with $R = 10$. The cluster is of circular shape with diameter equal to 165. The crack is moved away from the cluster in the horizontal direction and in the initial position the distance between the centre of the cluster and the centre of the crack is 125. For this particular configuration three different

distributions of fibers are generated within the cluster in order to determine the influence of various arrangements of fibers. The distributions are exposed to an unidirectional load applied at the remote boundaries in the vertical direction. The ratio between the Young's moduli for the matrix and fiber material is $E_a/E_m = 23$, and the Poisson ratios are $\nu_a = 0.3$ and $\nu_m = 0.35$. During the movement of the crack the stress intensity factor is determined and in the initial position the stress intensity factor is influenced by the exact arrangement of fibers. For larger distances between the cluster and the crack the effect of the exact position of fibers seems to be smeared out as there is no difference between the results for the three fibers distributions. Thus, for this particular configuration the stress intensity factor is independent of the exact distribution of fibers for $x > 200$. The second configuration also consists of a cluster of 26 fibers but now located below the crack, Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Stress intensity factors for the configuration where a cluster is located below a crack.

The similar effect is seen for this configuration, but here the stress intensity factor is not influenced by the exact position of fibers for $y > 350$. The configurations do not provide an exact estimate of the limit for short-range interaction but serve as an illustration of the problem.

FIBER DISTRIBUTIONS' EFFECT ON A NEIGHBOURING MACROCRACK

The relative position between fibers and the crack is crucial for the determination of the stress intensity factors. How the stress intensity factor changes depending on the relative position may be visualized by considering the stress field around a single fiber, Fig. 5.

The fiber is represented by the shaded area and contour lines are used to visualize the stress field, which is only calculated in the matrix material. The stress field at the position of a crack is responsible for the determination of stress intensity factor. Roughly speaking, if a crack or more precise the crack tip is situated along the stress line for which $\sigma_y = 1$, the normalized stress intensity factor equals one. Thus, in this case the existence of a fiber does not seem to affect the fracture toughness of the material. If a crack is situated in the area where $\sigma_y < 1$, the stress intensity factor is lower than one and thereby the material is toughened due to the fiber. On the contrary, if $\sigma_y > 1$ the material is softened because the stress intensity factor is higher than one. Of course the length of the crack enters the determination of stress intensity factors as an integration is performed over the whole length but as a guideline the stress field consideration is very useful.

Figure 5: Stress field around a fiber represented by constant stress lines.

The information of the stress field is only valid for one fiber in an infinite medium but may be used to derive a quantifier which is able to correlate the stress intensity factor for a crack situated in the vicinity of various fiber distributions with the spatial dispersion of fibers. This quantifier must take into account both distance and orientation between the fibers and the crack tip as these two parameters seem to be predominant. The following expression may be used as a quantifier

$$Q(r) = \sqrt{I(r)} \sum_{k=1}^{I(r)} \frac{1}{r_k^2} \text{sgn}(\theta_0 - |\theta_k|) \sqrt{|\theta_0 - |\theta_k||} \quad (13)$$

The function $Q(r)$ is called the *direct correlation function* where $I(r)$ is the number of fibers within a circle defined by radius r and a centre at the crack tip, Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Geometry used to calculate the quantifier.

r_k is the radial distance from the crack tip to the k 'th fiber. θ_k is the angle between the crack line and the k 'th fiber. θ_0 is the angle between the crack line and a fiber for which the stress intensity factor is unaffected. According to Fig. 5 θ_0 is approximately equal to 50° measured between the x -axis and the lower left stress line where $\sigma_y = 1$. The σ_y stress field is symmetrical both in horizontal and vertical direction.

The quantifier corresponds to the second-order intensity function, applied for the description of composite materials in Pyrz[5], and it may be used to separate different fiber distribution's effect on the stress intensity factors. Thus contrary to the second-order intensity function, which only takes into account the relative position of fibers, the $Q(r)$ function is related to a particular parameter, in this case the stress intensity factor.

The significance of the direct correlation function is illustrated by a crack situated in the vicinity of different fiber distributions. Distinct categories of distributions may be considered and in the following three hard-core distributions are analysed. The distributions, which include 50 fibers of radius 10, are generated within a sample area of 300×300 corresponding to a volume fraction of fibers equal to 17.5%. The crack is positioned besides the distributions with total crack length $2c = 60$. The stress intensity factors are calculated using the same material properties as in the previous section. Three distributions from the hard-core category are shown and the direct correlation function is determined, Fig. 7.

Figure 7: (a)-(c) Various distribution of the hard-core models, (d) direct correlation function.

The direct correlation function is able to differentiate between the three fiber distributions and the related stress intensity factors. Thus, the direct correlation function increases for an increased fracture toughness and vice versa. On a large scale the three distributions seem to be similar but observing the local areas near the crack tip a dissimilarity is detected. It is in these areas that the distribution of fibers has the largest influence corresponding to the short-range interaction. This is also accounted for in the direct correlation function by the factor $1/r_k^2$ and the sgn function. In the distribution shown in Fig. 7a fibers are located

closer to the crack tip than in the other distributions. This particular location results in a lowering of the stress intensity factor.

CONCLUSION

A method, for calculating the stress field in a solid containing randomly dispersed fibers as well as determination of the stress intensity factors for a crack situated among the fibers, has been applied.

The limit for short-range interaction can be estimated by considering simple configurations of a crack located in neighbourhood of fiber distributions. The analysis indicates the limit for when the exact position of fibers must be taken into account in the determination of stress intensity factors.

A quantifier, which is able to correlate the stress intensity factors with the geometrical arrangement of fibers, is established. The quantifier is valid for configurations consisting of a crack located in the vicinity of a fiber distribution. Whether the fracture toughness increases or decreases may be estimated by applying the quantifier. Therefore, descriptors that quantify the effect of the dispersion of fibers should become indispensable factors in the strength and fracture analysis of composite materials, Pyrz[6], Pyrz and Bochenek[7].

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